

Supplementary Figure 1: Determining intersects between curated disorder-type specific gene lists and genes from HPO and DisGeNET terms significantly enriched in curated lists

Supplementary Figure 2: Processing of EMBL-GWAS variants to generate psychiatric, neurological, and neurodevelopmental gene lists.

Supplementary Figure 3: Processing of ClinVar variants to generate psychiatric, neurological, and neurodevelopmental gene lists.

